

SLIDING MODE CONTROLLER DESIGN FOR SYNCHRONIZATION OF SHIMIZU-MORIOKA CHAOTIC SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the global chaos synchronization of identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems (Shimizu and Morioka, 1980) by sliding mode control. The stability results derived in this paper for the complete synchronization of identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems are established using Lyapunov stability theory. Since the Lyapunov exponents are not required for these calculations, the sliding mode control method is very effective and convenient to achieve global chaos synchronization of the identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems. Numerical simulations are shown to illustrate and validate the synchronization schemes derived in this paper for the identical Shimizu-Morioka systems.

KEYWORDS

Sliding Mode Control, Chaos Synchronization, Chaotic Systems, Shimizu-Morioka Systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chaotic systems are dynamical systems that are highly sensitive to initial conditions. The sensitive nature of chaotic systems is commonly called as the *butterfly effect* [1]. Synchronization of chaotic systems is a phenomenon which may occur when two or more chaotic oscillators are coupled or when a chaotic oscillator drives another chaotic oscillator. Because of the butterfly effect which causes the exponential divergence of the trajectories of two identical chaotic systems started with nearly the same initial conditions, synchronizing two chaotic systems is seemingly a very challenging problem.

In most of the chaos synchronization approaches, the *master-slave* or *drive-response* formalism is used. If a particular chaotic system is called the *master* or *drive* system and another chaotic system is called the *slave* or *response* system, then the idea of the synchronization is to use the output of the master system to control the slave system so that the output of the slave system tracks the output of the master system asymptotically.

Since the pioneering work by Pecora and Carroll ([2], 1990), chaos synchronization problem has been studied extensively and intensively in the literature [2-17]. Chaos theory has been applied to a variety of fields such as physical systems [3], chemical systems [4], ecological systems [5], secure communications [6-8], etc.

In the last two decades, various schemes have been successfully applied for chaos synchronization such as PC method [2], OGY method [9], active control method [10-12], adaptive control method [13-14], time-delay feedback method [15], backstepping design method [16], sampled-data feedback method [17], etc.

In this paper, we derive new results based on the sliding mode control [18-20] for the global chaos synchronization of identical Shimizu-Morioka systems ([21], Shimizu and Morioka, 1980). In robust control systems, the sliding mode control method is often adopted due to its inherent advantages of easy realization, fast response and good transient performance as well as its insensitivity to parameter uncertainties and external disturbances.

This paper has been organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the problem statement and our methodology using sliding mode control (SMC). In Section 3, we discuss the global chaos synchronization of identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems. In Section 4, we summarize the main results obtained in this paper.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND OUR METHODOLOGY USING SMC

In this section, we describe the problem statement for the global chaos synchronization for identical chaotic systems and our methodology using sliding mode control (SMC).

Consider the chaotic system described by

$$\dot{x} = Ax + f(x) \quad (1)$$

where $x \in R^n$ is the state of the system, A is the $n \times n$ matrix of the system parameters and $f : R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is the nonlinear part of the system.

We consider the system (1) as the *master* or *drive* system.

As the *slave* or *response* system, we consider the following chaotic system described by the dynamics

$$\dot{y} = Ay + f(y) + u \quad (2)$$

where $y \in R^n$ is the state of the system and $u \in R^m$ is the controller to be designed.

If we define the *synchronization error* as

$$e = y - x, \quad (3)$$

then the error dynamics is obtained as

$$\dot{e} = Ae + \eta(x, y) + u, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\eta(x, y) = f(y) - f(x) \quad (5)$$

The objective of the global chaos synchronization problem is to find a controller u such that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|e(t)\| = 0 \quad \text{for all } e(0) \in R^n.$$

To solve this problem, we first define the control u as

$$u = -\eta(x, y) + Bv \quad (6)$$

where B is a constant gain vector selected such that (A, B) is controllable.

Substituting (5) into (4), the error dynamics simplifies to

$$\dot{e} = Ae + Bv \quad (7)$$

which is a linear time-invariant control system with single input v .

Thus, the original global chaos synchronization problem can be replaced by an equivalent problem of stabilizing the zero solution $e = 0$ of the system (7) by a suitable choice of the sliding mode control. In the sliding mode control, we define the variable

$$s(e) = Ce = c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + \dots + c_n e_n \quad (8)$$

where $C = [c_1 \ c_2 \ \dots \ c_n]$ is a constant vector to be determined.

In the sliding mode control, we constrain the motion of the system (7) to the sliding manifold defined by

$$S = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid s(e) = 0\}$$

which is required to be invariant under the flow of the error dynamics (7).

When in sliding manifold S , the system (7) satisfies the following conditions:

$$s(e) = 0 \quad (9)$$

which is the defining equation for the manifold S and

$$\dot{s}(e) = 0 \quad (10)$$

which is the necessary condition for the state trajectory $e(t)$ of (7) to stay on the sliding manifold S .

Using (7) and (8), the equation (10) can be rewritten as

$$\dot{s}(e) = C[Ae + Bv] = 0 \quad (11)$$

Solving (11) for v , we obtain the equivalent control law

$$v_{eq}(t) = -(CB)^{-1}CA e(t) \quad (12)$$

where C is chosen such that $CB \neq 0$.

Substituting (12) into the error dynamics (7), we obtain the closed-loop dynamics as

$$\dot{e} = [I - B(CB)^{-1}C]Ae \quad (13)$$

The row vector C is selected such that the system matrix of the controlled dynamics $[I - B(CB)^{-1}C]A$ is Hurwitz, *i.e.* it has all eigenvalues with negative real parts. Then the controlled system (13) is globally asymptotically stable.

To design the sliding mode controller for (7), we apply the constant plus proportional rate reaching law

$$\dot{s} = -q \operatorname{sgn}(s) - k s \quad (14)$$

where $\operatorname{sgn}(\cdot)$ denotes the sign function and the gains $q > 0$, $k > 0$ are determined such that the sliding condition is satisfied and sliding motion will occur.

From equations (11) and (14), we can obtain the control $v(t)$ as

$$v(t) = -(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e + q \operatorname{sgn}(s)] \quad (15)$$

which yields

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} -(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e + q], & \text{if } s(e) > 0 \\ -(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e - q], & \text{if } s(e) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Theorem 1. *The master system (1) and the slave system (2) are globally and asymptotically synchronized for all initial conditions $x(0), y(0) \in R^n$ by the feedback control law*

$$u(t) = -\eta(x, y) + Bv(t) \quad (17)$$

where $v(t)$ is defined by (15) and B is a column vector such that (A, B) is controllable. Also, the sliding mode gains k, q are positive.

Proof. First, we note that substituting (17) and (15) into the error dynamics (4), we obtain the closed-loop error dynamics as

$$\dot{e} = Ae - B(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e + q \operatorname{sgn}(s)] \quad (18)$$

To prove that the error dynamics (18) is globally asymptotically stable, we consider the candidate Lyapunov function defined by the equation

$$V(e) = \frac{1}{2} s^2(e) \quad (19)$$

which is a positive definite function on R^n .

Differentiating V along the trajectories of (18) or the equivalent dynamics (14), we get

$$\dot{V}(e) = s(e)\dot{s}(e) = -ks^2 - q\text{sgn}(s)s \quad (20)$$

which is a negative definite function on R^n .

This calculation shows that V is a globally defined, positive definite, Lyapunov function for the error dynamics (18), which has a globally defined, negative definite time derivative \dot{V} .

Thus, by Lyapunov stability theory [22], it is immediate that the error dynamics (18) is globally asymptotically stable for all initial conditions $e(0) \in R^n$.

This means that for all initial conditions $e(0) \in R^n$, we have

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|e(t)\| = 0$$

Hence, it follows that the master system (1) and the slave system (2) are globally and asymptotically synchronized for all initial conditions $x(0), y(0) \in R^n$.

This completes the proof. ■

3. GLOBAL SYNCHRONIZATION OF IDENTICAL SHIMIZU-MORIOKA CHAOTIC SYSTEMS USING SLIDING MODE CONTROL

3.1 Theoretical Results

In this section, we apply the sliding mode control results derived in Section 2 for the global chaos synchronization of identical Shimizu-Morioka (SM) chaotic systems ([21], Shimizu and Morioka, 1980).

Thus, the master system is described by the SM dynamics

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= x_2 \\ \dot{x}_2 &= x_1 - \lambda x_2 - x_1 x_3 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= x_1^2 - \xi x_3 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where x_1, x_2, x_3 are state variables and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \omega$ are positive, constant parameters of the system.

The slave system is described by the controlled SM dynamics

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{y}_1 &= y_2 + u_1 \\ \dot{y}_2 &= y_1 - \lambda y_2 - y_1 y_3 + u_2 \\ \dot{y}_3 &= y_1^2 - \xi y_3 + u_3 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where y_1, y_2, y_3 are state variables and u_1, u_2, u_3 are the controllers to be designed.

The Shimizu-Morioka systems (21) and (22) are chaotic when $\lambda = 0.75$ and $\xi = 0.45$.

Figure 1 illustrates the double-wing butterfly-shaped attractor of the SM system (21).

Figure 1. State Orbits of the Shimizu-Morioka Chaotic System

The chaos synchronization error is defined by

$$e_i = y_i - x_i, \quad (i = 1, 2, 3) \quad (23)$$

The error dynamics is easily obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1 &= e_2 + u_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 &= e_1 - \lambda e_2 - y_1 y_3 + x_1 x_3 + u_2 \\ \dot{e}_3 &= -\xi e_3 + y_1^2 - x_1^2 + u_3 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

We write the error dynamics (24) in the matrix notation as

$$\dot{e} = Ae + \eta(x, y) + u \quad (25)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -\lambda & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\xi \end{bmatrix}, \quad \eta(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -y_1 y_3 + x_1 x_3 \\ y_1^2 - x_1^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad u = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

The sliding mode controller design is carried out as detailed in Section 2.

First, we set u as

$$u = -\eta(x, y) + Bv \quad (27)$$

where B is chosen such that (A, B) is controllable.

We take B as

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (28)$$

In the chaotic case, the parameter values are

$$\lambda = 0.75 \quad \text{and} \quad \xi = 0.45.$$

The sliding mode variable is selected as

$$s = Ce = [2 \quad 1 \quad -2]e = 2e_1 + e_2 - 2e_3 \quad (29)$$

which makes the sliding mode state equation asymptotically stable.

We choose the sliding mode gains as $k = 5$ and $q = 0.1$.

We note that a large value of k can cause chattering and an appropriate value of q is chosen to speed up the time taken to reach the sliding manifold as well as to reduce the system chattering.

From Eq. (15), we can obtain $v(t)$ as

$$v(t) = -11 e_1 - 6.25e_2 + 9.1 e_3 - 0.1 \operatorname{sgn}(s) \quad (30)$$

Thus, the required sliding mode controller is obtained as

$$u = -\eta(x, y) + Bv \quad (31)$$

where $\eta(x, y)$, B and $v(t)$ are defined as in the equations (26), (28) and (30).

By Theorem 1, we obtain the following result.

Theorem 2. *The identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems (21) and (22) are globally and asymptotically synchronized for all initial conditions with the sliding mode controller u defined by (31). ■*

3.2 Numerical Results

In this section For the numerical simulations, the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method with time-step $h = 10^{-6}$ is used to solve the Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems (21) and (22) with the sliding mode controller u given by (31) using MATLAB.

In the chaotic case, the parameter values are

$$\lambda = 0.75 \quad \text{and} \quad \xi = 0.45.$$

The sliding mode gains are chosen as

$$k = 5 \quad \text{and} \quad q = 0.1.$$

The initial values of the master system (21) are taken as

$$x_1(0) = 30, \quad x_2(0) = 25, \quad x_3(0) = 14$$

and the initial values of the slave system (22) are taken as

$$y_1(0) = 4, \quad y_2(0) = 18, \quad y_3(0) = 20$$

Figure 2 illustrates the complete synchronization of the identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems (21) and (22).

Figure 2. Synchronization of Identical Shimizu-Morioka Chaotic Systems

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have deployed sliding mode control (SMC) to achieve global chaos synchronization for the identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems (1980). Our synchronization results for the identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems have been proved using Lyapunov stability theory. Since the Lyapunov exponents are not required for these calculations, the sliding mode control method is very effective and convenient to achieve global chaos synchronization for the identical Shimizu-Morioka chaotic systems. Numerical simulations are also shown to illustrate the effectiveness of the synchronization results derived in this paper using the sliding mode control.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alligood, K.T., Sauer, T. & Yorke, J.A. (1997) *Chaos: An Introduction to Dynamical Systems*, Springer, New York.
- [2] Pecora, L.M. & Carroll, T.L. (1990) "Synchronization in chaotic systems", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 64, pp 821-824.
- [3] Lakshmanan, M. & Murali, K. (1996) *Nonlinear Oscillators: Controlling and Synchronization*, World Scientific, Singapore.
- [4] Han, S.K., Kerrer, C. & Kuramoto, Y. (1995) "Dephasing and bursting in coupled neural oscillators", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 75, pp 3190-3193.
- [5] Blasius, B., Huppert, A. & Stone, L. (1999) "Complex dynamics and phase synchronization in spatially extended ecological system", *Nature*, Vol. 399, pp 354-359.
- [6] Cuomo, K.M. & Oppenheim, A.V. (1993) "Circuit implementation of synchronized chaos with applications to communications," *Physical Review Letters*, Vol. 71, pp 65-68.
- [7] Kocarev, L. & Parlitz, U. (1995) "General approach for chaotic synchronization with applications to communication," *Physical Review Letters*, Vol. 74, pp 5028-5030.
- [8] Tao, Y. (1999) "Chaotic secure communication systems – history and new results," *Telecommun. Review*, Vol. 9, pp 597-634.
- [9] Ott, E., Grebogi, C. & Yorke, J.A. (1990) "Controlling chaos", *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, Vol. 64, pp 1196-1199.
- [10] Ho, M.C. & Hung, Y.C. (2002) "Synchronization of two different chaotic systems using generalized active network," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 301, pp 424-428.
- [11] Huang, L., Feng, R. & Wang, M. (2005) "Synchronization of chaotic systems via nonlinear control," *Physical Letters A*, Vol. 320, pp 271-275.
- [12] Chen, H.K. (2005) "Global chaos synchronization of new chaotic systems via nonlinear control," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 23, pp 1245-1251.
- [13] Lu, J., Wu, X., Han, X. & Lü, J. (2004) "Adaptive feedback synchronization of a unified chaotic system," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 329, pp 327-333.
- [14] Chen, S.H. & Lü, J. (2002) "Synchronization of an uncertain unified system via adaptive control," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 14, pp 643-647.
- [15] Park, J.H. & Kwon, O.M. (2003) "A novel criterion for delayed feedback control of time-delay chaotic systems," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 17, pp 709-716.
- [16] Wu, X. & Lü, J. (2003) "Parameter identification and backstepping control of uncertain Lü system," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 18, pp 721-729.
- [17] Zhao, J. & J. Lu (2006) "Using sampled-data feedback control and linear feedback synchronization in a new hyperchaotic system," *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals*, Vol. 35, pp 376-382.

- [18] Slotine, J.E. & Sastry, S.S. (1983) "Tracking control of nonlinear systems using sliding surface with application to robotic manipulators," *Internat. J. Control*, Vol. 38, pp 465-492.
- [19] Utkin, V.I. (1993) "Sliding mode control design principles and applications to electric drives," *IEEE Trans. Industrial Electronics*, Vol. 40, pp 23-36, 1993.
- [20] Saravanakumar, R., Vinoth Kumar, K. & Ray, K.K. (2009) "Sliding mode control of induction motor using simulation approach," *Internat. J. Control of Comp. Sci. Network Security*, Vol. 9, pp 93-104.
- [21] Shimizu, T. & Morioka, N. (1980) "On the bifurcation of a symmetric limit cycle to an asymmetric one in a simple model," *Physics Letters A*, Vol. 76, pp. 201-204.
- [22] Hahn, W. (1967) *The Stability of Motion*, Springer, New York.

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